

AN APPROACH TO ENHANCE THE DATA CLEANSING METHOD IN BIG DATA APPLICATION

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Abstract

Nowadays, massive amounts of data are available for the organization which will influence their business decision. Data collected from the various resources are dirty and this will affect the accuracy of prediction result. Data cleansing offers a better data quality which will be a great help for the organization to make sure their data is ready for the analysing phase. However, the amount of data collected by the organizations has been increasing every year, which is making most of the existing approach is not suitable for Big Data. Generally, data cleaning consist of identifying the errors, detecting the errors and correct them. These processes are done iteratively until all the data is cleaned. Despite the data need to be analyses quickly, the data cleansing process is complex and time consuming in order to make sure the cleaned data meet the data quality dimension. In this paper, a preliminary discussion on the data cleansing for big data application has been provided. The main problems found in data cleansing is the time required for data cleansing and the veracity of the data is highlighted. We are currently looking for ways to improve these problems found in order to increase the quality of data.

1 INTRODUCTION

Big Data is no longer a buzzword among the business organization. The amount of data

collected and stored by the organizations around the world has been increasing every year. This phenomenon has generates terabytes of data in various format such as structured data and unstructured data which is making the data cleansing becoming more difficult.

Data cleansing is defined as the process that consists of detecting, identifying, and imputing anomalous data [1]. It deals with the errors, missing values and inconsistencies within the data in order to improve the quality of data. It is also important for every business that aims to identify the patterns and extract valuable information from the collected data.

Quality data only can be produced by data cleansing since the data collected from the various sources might be dirty [2]. Poor data quality can lead to inaccurate result and may result in misguided decision. The companies need to ensure their data is accurate to avoid losses, problems and cost due to poor quality of data. For example, 75% of 599 companies have suffered losses due to data quality issue according to the “Price Waterhouse Coopers” survey conducted in 2001 in New York [3]. Since the business is depend on the data like customer relationship management and supply chain management, thus it is important for them to have a better quality data for more accurate and valuable result.

Based on the report by Crowdflower [4], access to the quality data is the main issue faced by

data scientist to complete their work. Besides, Data quality experts estimate that a business spends about 40 to 50% of the budget for the data cleansing process as it is time-consuming, labor-intensive and tedious processes [5].

Data quality can be measured using a quality dimension which includes accuracy, completeness, timeliness and consistency. The explanations for each characteristic are as follows [3]:

- Accuracy - conformity of the recorded value with the actual value
- Timeliness - the recorded value is not out of date
- Completeness - all values for a certain variable are recorded;
- Consistency – the representation of data is uniform in all cases.

Data cleansing process is complex and consist of several stages which include specifying the quality rules, detecting data error and repairing the error [1]. This process is done iteratively since the data is being collected continuously. The process of data cleansing is illustrated in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Data Cleansing Process [3]

Data cleansing in no longer new research field and various research have been done throughout the years to find the ultimate data cleansing tools to solve data quality issue. However, this is not an easy task as the amount of data is increasing every day and the existing approach will no longer able to cope with this situation.

2 PROPOSED WORK

Despite all the tools being introduced for data cleansing, data scientist still finds its time consuming. According to Crowdflower [4], collecting, labeling, cleaning and organizing the data takes up about 51% of their time. This janitorial task is the least favorite by most of them.

Besides, the veracity of the cleaned data is the main concern where the cleaned data should increase the data quality and decrease the operational risk. However, the cleaned data still doubtful as no model or standard technique has been identified to clean big data and domain expert is required most of the time.

In order to address the issue raised in the data cleansing process, we proposed a new approach that can solve all these problems in data cleansing. The objectives of this research are as follows:

1. To design an approach that can improve the time required for data cleansing.
2. To design and approach that can improve the veracity of the data.
3. To implement and validate the new approach.

We hope that by enhancing the data cleansing process, the time required by the data scientist to clean the data is reduced. Moreover, the trustworthiness of the organizations towards the result obtained from the quality data is important which will provide huge benefits to the organization itself.

Since the proposed work still in the proposal phase, thus further research on the related work is needed to support the proposed work.

References

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